

Slum Sisterhood, philanthropy and Sapphic dialogues in Margaret Harkness's *In Darkest London* (1890)

Garth Wenman-James (g.wenman-james@surrey.ac.uk)

Introduction: Sisterhood, Charity, and the Slums

My research focusses on three main elements of the slum novel in the late nineteenth century:

New Horizons: By the mid-1890s, **over half a million women** in Britain were 'occupied continuously' in philanthropic work (Poole, 2014, p. 3). Up until this point, philanthropic efforts in the slums were often led by clergymen and doctors—**typically male occupations**. Known as 'slum sisterhoods', these groups of women **crafted new horizons** that made way for **major reforms of the Poor Laws** as well as laying foundations for later **suffrage** movements.

Poverty Porn: Novels like Margaret Harkness's *In Darkest London* (1890) represent the **social reform enacted** by these women. Yet, they also act as a form of **entertainment**, or 'poverty porn', to **evoke pleasure** in readers.

Sex and Desire in the Slums: The eroticisation of poverty in the slum novel appears in dialogue with Harkness's use of the slum space to express 'Sapphic desire', an expression of **sexual or emotional passion between women** (Vanita, 1996).

Margaret Harkness: Slum Sister, Socialist, Philanthropist

- > Margaret Harkness was a **socialist, philanthropist, nurse, novelist and journalist** working towards social reform at the end of the nineteenth century
- > Harkness saw the perceived divides between religious (**the Salvation Army**) and secular (**socialist**) philanthropic groups as detrimental to improving the conditions of the poor, stating that the **'two organisations ought to work more together than they do at present, they have many points of common interest'** (1888, p. 2).
- > *In Darkest London* follows the lives of women in the Salvation Army as well as socialist sisterhoods, emphasising the social **progress that can be achieved with both groups working together**. The title is taken from the Salvation Army manifesto *In Darkest England and the Way Out* (1890), further indicating the influence that this context had on Harkness's novel writing
- > As a socialist herself, Harkness worked as a slum sister alongside **Beatrice Webb** and **Eleanor Marx**, both highly influential figures on social reform and economic theory (Ross, 2007, p. 90). Harkness's experience with slum work sets her writing apart from the slum novels of Arthur Morrison and Elizabeth Gaskell.

Slumming together: Passionate dialogues and Sapphic relations among slum sisterhoods

Slum sisters enacted social change by **'dressing, walking, and writing together'** (Rappoport, 2012, p. 136). In these same-sex communities, a Sapphic dialogue was produced; according to Ruth Vanita (1996), the Sapphic mode refers to a **same-sex desire** created between women through social action and shared sympathetic experience. Harkness herself alludes to something much like Sapphic desire in a letter to Beatrice Webb, where she defined love as the mixture between **'sympathy + kindred feeling'** (1887); this is represented throughout *In Darkest London*, with the protagonist Ruth managing to cross from secular to religious sisterhoods. In sharing the sympathies of both sisterhoods, Ruth assists them in their **'crusade against poverty'** (1890, p. 73). Reflecting on the sisters' project to enact change in the slums, Harkness's narrator concludes that:

"Never since the world began has there been seen such an attempt as these girls are making at present" (1890, p. 73)

Sapphic desire and Masochism

- > In much the same way that *In Darkest London* operates a form of poverty porn which **evokes pleasure** from the reader through its images of grotesque poverty, the Slum Sisters gain pleasure from their work in the slums.
- > Speaking of the slum sisters, an unnamed pauper states that **'you can't scare those girls [...] it's not good trying to scare em', they just enjoys it'** (p. 180). A shared masochism (the experience of pleasure when faced with pain or danger) occurs among the slum sisters, who 'enjoy' the danger posed by the poor they attempt to assist.
- > Masochism of this form features within Sapphic, same-sex desire as a **shared pleasurable experience** (Prins, 1999, p. 155). The slum sisters themselves therefore experience the novel's environment as **poverty porn**.

Conclusions

In Darkest London represents Harkness's attempt to summarise the **bonds between women** within same-sex philanthropic communities, as well as the new horizons crafted by these women; through their 'crusade against poverty', the slum sisters **enabled economic change**, while also emphasising the integral nature of their **own voices** in a largely male-dominated culture. Yet, Harkness also represents the almost pornographic **pleasure** that can be garnered from slum work. As poverty porn, her novel recognises the pleasures that can be gained by entering the slums and **gazing at the poor**. In Harkness's novel, and the Victorian slum novel generally, **social change and poverty are intertwined with pleasure**. My close analysis of Harkness's novel illustrates that while the novel is mostly concerned with the **social good slum sisterhoods performed throughout the late nineteenth century**, these communities actually provided **power, agency and pleasure** for the women themselves rather than the poor they **claimed** to be assisting.

Bibliography:

- Booth, W. (1890) *In Darkest England and the Way Out*. London: Funk & Wagnalls.
- Harkness, M. (1875) Letter to Beatrice Webb, 10 December. *British Library of Political and Economic Science*, Passfield Papers, PASSFIELD/2/1/2/2, ff. 34.
- Harkness, M. (1888) 'Salvationists and Socialists', in *Justice*, 24 March 1888. London. p. 2.
- Harkness, M. (1890) *In Darkest London*. London: Black Apollo Press.
- Poole, A.G. (2014) *Philanthropy and the Construction of Victorian Women's Citizenship: Lady Frederick Cavendish and Miss Emma Cons*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press.
- Prins, Y. (1999) *Victorian Sappho*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Rappoport, J. (2012) 'Service and Saving in the Slums', in *Giving Women: Alliance and Exchange in Victorian Culture*. New York: Oxford University Press. pp. 107 – 138. doi: 10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199772605.001.0001
- Ross, E. (2007) 'Margaret Harkness', in *Slum Travelers: Ladies and London Poverty, 1860-1920*. Berkeley: University of California Press. pp. 89 – 96.
- Vanita, R. (1996) *Sappho and the Virgin Mary*. New York: Columbia University Press.